

Zero-shot point cloud segmentation for hydro power plant components

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Funding information

HORIZON EUROPE Framework Programme, Grant/Award Number: 101122357; European Union

Abstract

Accurate 3D segmentation of hydro power plant (HPP) components from point cloud data is essential for building high-fidelity digital twin systems that enable automation in construction, monitoring, and maintenance. However, existing point cloud segmentation methods suffer from high annotation costs. To address these challenges, a novel fully automated segmentation framework is proposed that assigns 3D semantic labels directly from unannotated point cloud data using only a textual prompt, without prior training on HPP-specific data. Experiments on six real-world HPP scenarios demonstrate that it achieves superior performance compared to state-of-the-art zero-shot baselines, with an average positive ratio of 72.56% and negative ratio of 20.45%, while significantly reducing the human effort and time required for segmentation. This study advances automation in construction by providing a practical, annotation-free solution for large-scale, fine-grained 3D segmentation of complex HPP environments, laying the foundation for efficient, intelligent digital twin creation and automated decision support in hydropower engineering.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Hydro power plants (HPP) point cloud segmentation is a key foundation for building digital twin (DT) platforms. According to the International Energy Agency's (2024) report, HPPs account for 14.3% of global electricity generation, making them one of the largest sources of renewable energy. They are also contributing to the achievement of carbon neutrality goals, flood control, irrigation, and water resource management (Liu et al., 2019; Schmitt & Rosa, 2024). In recent years, the emergence of DT technology has introduced new ideas and methods for the planning of hydropower construction projects (Sleiti et al., 2022). By constructing virtual digital models,

DT technology enables lifecycle simulation and optimization of hydropower projects (Ersan & Irmak, 2024). Point cloud segmentation provides the geometric foundation for these DTs by accurately identifying key structural components (Davletshina et al., 2024; Pan et al., 2024) such as dams, tunnels, and powerhouses, thereby supporting monitoring, maintenance, and decision-making.

However, existing point cloud segmentation methods face numerous challenges when applied to HPP point cloud segmentation tasks:

(1) Manual segmentation is labor-intensive. HPP point cloud data typically exhibit highly complex structural features (Liu et al., 2016; Ramos & Coronado-Hernández, 2023), including irregular dam surfaces, intricate water

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flow channels, and mechanical equipment inside powerhouses. Due to the structural diversity and detail richness of hydropower station scenes, traditional manual segmentation methods are time-consuming, labor-intensive, and prone to subjective bias (Kamari & Ham, 2021). As a result, the consistency of segmentation results among different annotators is often unreliable, limiting their suitability for efficient and precise DT construction.

(2) Point cloud segmentation methods based on rules and traditional geometric features lack robustness. These methods mainly rely on geometric features (e.g., normal, curvature, plane fitting), and commonly used approaches include region-growing (Vo et al., 2015), RANSAC (Schnabel et al., 2007), and clustering-based methods (e.g., DBSCAN; Chen et al., 2022). HPP point cloud data often include complex surfaces (such as irregular dam structures), making it difficult for rule-based methods to accurately identify highly complex structures. Moreover, these methods are sensitive to noise in the point cloud, which can result in misclassification.

(3) Supervised learning-based point cloud segmentation methods require large amounts of labeled data. Many advanced point cloud segmentation methods rely on deep learning, but annotating HPP point cloud data is extremely costly (Ibrahim et al., 2021; Meng et al., 2021). Annotating HPP point clouds requires expert knowledge, making data labeling costly and time-consuming. Moreover, limited dataset size and scene diversity hinder supervised models from achieving robust performance (Shah et al., 2025).

(4) Existing unsupervised learning methods for point cloud segmentation are difficult to apply to HPP scenarios. Although some existing unsupervised methods have achieved promising results on public datasets—such as PointContrast (Xie et al., 2020), GrowSP (Zhang et al., 2023), and UnScene3D (Rozenberszki et al., 2024)—they have clear limitations in real-world engineering applications. These methods often require a certain amount of training data and rely on auxiliary information beyond the point cloud itself, such as multi-view RGB images (Liang et al., 2022), depth maps or dynamic sequences (Song et al., 2022), to construct contrastive views, spatial consistency, or self-supervised signals. However, in complex industrial environments like HPPs, such multimodal data are often difficult to obtain or unreliable in quality, making current methods hard to deploy directly. Especially in environments lacking support from additional sensors and with restricted data acquisition conditions, relying solely on point cloud data for effective segmentation becomes even more challenging.

(5) Current models with zero-shot capabilities are extremely limited. Given the high annotation cost and

complexity of HPP data, zero-shot segmentation methods offer a highly promising direction by eliminating the need for extensive labeled datasets (Ren et al., 2023; Siriborvornratanakul, 2024). However, only a few methods, such as RE0 (Anonymous, 2024) and SAM3D (Yang et al., 2023), claim to perform point cloud semantic inference on previously unseen data or categories. These methods still rely on external information like RGB-D images and camera poses for model training. Furthermore, their designs are primarily intended for natural images or general-purpose scenes (Anonymous, 2024; Yang et al., 2023), lacking structural understanding and semantic modeling for HPP engineering objects. When faced with industrial point clouds that include complex components, strong geometric similarity, and multi-scale structures—as in HPPs—these models often fail to deliver fine-grained and semantically consistent segmentation results. Therefore, there is an urgent need for a scene-specific zero-shot 3D segmentation model that operates solely on point cloud data to meet the requirements for high-precision and high-robustness segmentation in HPP DT systems.

To address these challenges, this paper proposes zero-shot point cloud segmentation for hydro power plant (ZPSH)—a zero-shot semantic segmentation framework designed specifically for hydropower environments. The method supports end-to-end deployment and enables semantic inference directly on previously unseen individual HPP point cloud scenes. Unlike existing methods that rely on multimodal auxiliary data or retraining on new scenes, ZPSH operates solely on point cloud data and leverages semantic guidance through domain-specific textual prompts. The model integrates a pre-trained large vision–language foundation model with multi-view point cloud rendering, visual–language alignment, and a cross-view self-learning module to achieve accurate 3D semantic segmentation without annotation or fine-tuning. The main contributions of this study are: (1) a zero-shot segmentation approach that requires only point cloud data, eliminating dependence on RGB-D or multimodal inputs; (2) a novel cross-view self-learning mechanism enhancing semantic and geometric consistency across viewpoints; and (3) comprehensive validation on real HPP datasets, demonstrating superior accuracy and robustness over existing baselines.

The remaining parts of this paper are organized as follows: In Section 2, related works are reviewed. Section 3 introduced the framework and details of the ZPSH model, and Section 4 provides the experimental data preparation and results. Section 5 discusses the segmentation cases, limitations of the current study, and perspective works in the future. Finally, Section 6 summarizes the study.

2 | RELATED WORKS

2.1 | Point cloud segmentation in HPP scenarios

Recent advances in machine learning have demonstrated significant potential in civil and structural engineering, from unsupervised health condition assessment of infrastructures (Rafiei & Adeli, 2018) to data-driven prediction of windstorm-induced responses in long-span bridges (Entezami & Sarmadi, 2025). These studies highlight the growing role of AI-based models in analyzing complex structural behaviors and motivate their extension to spatially rich, 3D environments such as hydropower plants. However, the HPP environments pose unique challenges for 3D point cloud segmentation. In such industrial settings, point clouds often capture large-scale facilities (dam body, turbines, pipes, tunnels, etc.) with complex geometry and clutter. Early approaches to segmenting these point clouds were predominantly manual. Experts would manually annotate regions corresponding to different structural components (Dimitrov et al., 2015). This labor-intensive process is error-prone and infeasible for dense, expansive HPP data. Traditional automation techniques therefore emerged, relying on geometric heuristics and clustering. For example, region-growing or model-fitting algorithms can segment simple primitives (fitting planes to walls or cylinders to pipes), and spatial clustering (e.g., Euclidean distance-based clustering) can separate disconnected parts (Su, 2015; Sun, 2013). While these classical methods require no training data, they struggle with the intricate and unstructured nature of HPP scenes. Components that lack distinctive geometric cues or are partially occluded often remain incorrectly merged or fragmented.

The advent of machine learning brought supervised segmentation methods that significantly improved accuracy on 3D point clouds (Yang et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2023). By training deep networks (e.g., PointNet and sparse 3D CNNs) on large, annotated datasets, researchers achieved high-quality semantic and instance segmentation in domains such as industrial facilities (Agapaki & Brilakis, 2020, 2021). However, supervised learning demands extensive point-level labeling, which is a costly and time-consuming endeavor, especially for specialized environments. Manually annotating a single 3D scan can take tens of minutes or more, and creating a comprehensive labeled dataset for a complex HPP site is impractical (Davletshina et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2016). Moreover, models trained on standard datasets (e.g., ScanNet (Dai et al., 2017), SemanticKITTI (Behley et al., 2019)) may not generalize to a power plant's novel structures and outdoor/industrial conditions. As a result, directly applying off-the-shelf supervised models to HPP data often yields

suboptimal results. This gap has motivated interest in zero-shot 3D segmentation techniques, which can help organize point clouds without intensive labeling efforts. Beyond segmentation, machine learning has shown tangible value in civil infrastructure applications, e.g., unsupervised deep learning for global and local structural health assessment (Rafiei & Adeli, 2018) and ML-aided prediction of windstorm-induced vibration responses of long-span suspension bridges (Entezami & Sarmadi, 2025). These studies underscore the practical impact of data-driven methods and motivate our zero-shot, retraining-free design for HPP assets.

2.2 | Unsupervised and zero-shot point cloud segmentation

Unsupervised and zero-shot segmentation represent two fundamentally different approaches to point cloud segmentation, especially for scenarios with limited labeled data. Unsupervised segmentation aims to partition point clouds into distinct regions without using any labeled data. These methods typically rely on geometric features, clustering, or self-supervised learning, and the resulting segments usually lack semantic meaning (Rozenberszki et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2024). In contrast, zero-shot segmentation seeks to assign semantic labels to points from categories that the model has never seen during training. This is often achieved by leveraging cross-modal knowledge, such as combining 3D point features with language models or textual prompts (Tang et al., 2025; Yang et al., 2023; Zhong et al., 2024). While unsupervised methods focus on structural grouping, zero-shot techniques aim at semantic generalization to unseen classes. It is worth noting that this study focuses on semantic segmentation, where each 3D point is assigned a class-level label corresponding to a structural component (e.g., spillway, crest, and access road), rather than instance segmentation, which aims to distinguish individual object instances of the same class.

Table 1 presents a comprehensive comparison of current unsupervised and zero-shot 3D segmentation methods, revealing critical limitations that hinder their applicability in HPP environments. Most unsupervised methods rely heavily on geometric clustering (Zhang et al., 2023) or contrastive pretraining (Xie et al., 2020) and must be retrained for each dataset or scene, resulting in poor scalability and a lack of semantic interpretability. These approaches are difficult to apply in HPP environments, where scenes are large, heterogeneous, and dynamically changing. Other unsupervised models like ONeRF (Liang et al., 2022) and UnScene3D (Liu et al., 2024) also require per-scene or per-dataset optimization and cannot generalize to new

TABLE 1 Comparison of existing unsupervised and zero-shot 3D segmentation learning methods.

Model	Method description	Limitations
Unsupervised models		
Point contrast (Xie et al., 2020)	Unsupervised contrastive learning for 3D point cloud pretraining; learns point-level features by matching across augmented views.	Requires pretraining on target dataset and does not perform tasks directly without training.
Point cloud co-segmentation (Yang et al., 2021)	Uses co-contrastive learning and mutual attention to co-segment common parts in point clouds; retrains on each new object group.	Needs training on each input set; no generalization to unseen categories without retraining.
OGC (Song et al., 2022)	Unsupervised 3D object segmentation based on rigid dynamics from scene flow without labels.	Requires training per dataset; does not generalize directly to new tasks.
ONeRF (Liang et al., 2022)	Unsupervised object-aware NeRF optimized per scene using the EM algorithm.	Requires scene-specific training; does not perform zero-shot generalization.
GrowSP (Zhang et al., 2023)	Unsupervised semantic segmentation using superpoint growing, clustering, and geometric consistency.	Trained from scratch on each dataset; lacks zero-shot generalization.
UnScene3D (Rozenberszki et al., 2024)	Unsupervised 3D instance segmentation using geometric over-segmentation and self-training.	Trains on each dataset with pseudo labels; not capable of zero-shot task execution.
U3DS3 (Liu et al., 2024)	Fully unsupervised 3D semantic segmentation using clustering and consistency constraints.	Requires full unsupervised training per dataset; lacks zero-shot generalization.
FreePoint (Zhang et al., 2024)	Graph-based unsupervised point cloud segmentation with pseudo labels and stepwise weak supervision.	Does not generalize across datasets without retraining; requires pseudo-label training.
Zero-shot models		
SAM3D (Yang et al., 2023)	Performs zero-shot 3D segmentation by projecting 2D masks from SAM into 3D via RGB-D images and camera poses.	Requires RGB images, depth maps, and camera intrinsics; cannot work with point clouds alone.
SATR (Abdelreheem et al., 2023)	Detects part masks in rendered 2D views using GLIP and maps them to 3D meshes via topology-aware fusion.	Needs RGB rendering and mesh inputs; point clouds must be pre-processed into meshes.
REO (Anonymous, 2024)	Uses CLIP and Crop Former to detect objects in 2D views and transfers masks into 3D using depth and pose information.	Heavily depends on multi-view RGB-D and accurate poses; not applicable with point clouds only.
MeshSegmenter (Zhong et al., 2024)	Combines 2D segmentation results with 3D meshes by projecting multi-view masks onto mesh surfaces.	Requires mesh geometry and rendered RGB images; point clouds alone are insufficient.
Point-SAM (Zhou et al., 2024)	Native 3D promotable segmentation model designed for point clouds. It utilizes a transformer-based architecture with a novel Voronoi tokenizer, supports both point and mask prompts, and is trained on a mix of real and synthetic datasets with pseudo labels distilled from SAM. Enables interactive segmentation, zero-shot transfer, and instance proposals directly on point clouds.	While capable of zero-shot segmentation on raw point clouds, it still depends on RGB-D data, which is hard to obtain in HPP scenarios. High computational cost due to transformer architecture and scalability to very large scenes remains challenging.
ZeroPS (Xue et al., 2025)	Transfers 2D masks from rendered multi-view images into 3D mesh space using bidirectional projection.	Requires rendered images and mesh geometry; cannot process raw point clouds alone.
OnlineAnySeg (Tang et al., 2025)	Streams RGB-D frames to build 3D segmentation maps using 2D foundation models and back-projection.	Relies on continuous RGB-D input and poses; does not support standalone point cloud input.

environments, limiting their practical use for varied and unstructured HPP sites where flexibility is key.

Zero-shot approaches, while more flexible, usually depend on auxiliary modalities such as RGB-D images, camera intrinsics, or mesh geometry to project 2D masks into 3D space, such as SAM3D (Yang et al., 2023), REO (Anonymous, 2024), and ZeroPS (Xue et al., 2025). However, in real-world HPP applications, raw LiDAR or laser-

based point clouds are often the only available data, with no reliable RGB or mesh input due to environmental constraints like lighting, occlusions, or large-scale machinery. These methods, therefore, cannot be directly applied without extensive preprocessing or sensor fusion infrastructure, which is often unavailable in field operations.

Recent advances such as SAM2Point (Guo et al., 2024), Omni-Scan2BIM (Wang et al., 2024), and SAM4TUN

(Ye et al., 2025) have extended SAM-based segmentation from 2D imagery to 3D point clouds and engineering applications. However, these methods remain constrained by task-specific assumptions that limit their generalization to complex hydropower environments. SAM2Point relies on explicit 3D prompts such as points, boxes, or masks to drive geometric segmentation, which is impractical for large-scale and irregular HPP structures where manual or structured prompting cannot be efficiently applied. Omni-Scan2BIM performs one-shot segmentation for MEP scenes using visual similarity maps derived from a single reference image, but its shape priors and single-sample dependency make it unsuitable for irregular, large-scale HPP geometries. SAM4TUN unfolds cylindrical tunnel linings into 2D panoramas and applies SAM with template-based prompts, a design tailored to repetitive and regular structures that cannot generalize to unstructured HPP components such as spillways or slopes. In contrast, ZPSH eliminates these dependencies by enabling text-prompt-based, modality-independent segmentation directly on raw 3D point clouds.

In conclusion, existing segmentation methods either lack generalization to unseen data or depend on data modalities not accessible in typical HPP settings. PointSAM (Zhou et al., 2024) stands out as a native 3D segmentation model that supports zero-shot inference directly on point clouds, but its training still relies on RGB-D data, which limits its applicability in HPP environments where such data are often unavailable. This underscores the need for point cloud segmentation approaches that are modality-independent, retraining-free, and capable of directly handling unstructured 3D data in complex industrial environments like HPP.

3 | METHODOLOGY

3.1 | Framework

The proposed ZPSH method consists of three core steps, as shown in Figure 1: (1) 3D to 2D transformation: Centered on the HPP point cloud model, the 3D point cloud data are projected into multiple 2D RGB images from different viewpoints. During this process, the correspondence between each 3D point and its associated 2D pixel in the images is recorded. (2) Prompt-guided segmentation: Leveraging the semantic understanding capabilities of the contrastive language-image pretraining (CLIP) (Radford et al., 2021) model, a text prompt is aligned with the image feature space and compared against the multi-view RGB images generated in step 1. This comparison identifies the pixels most semantically aligned with the prompt,

which are then selected as guidance points. The coordinates of these guidance points are fed into the SAM2 (Ravi et al., 2024) model to produce segmentation masks based on HPP-specific semantic understanding. Among the multiple candidate masks generated, ZPSH employs a newly proposed cross-view self-learning module, specifically designed to determine the optimal masked images from all viewpoints. (3) Reverse mapping: Using the selected optimal masked images from step 2, along with the previously recorded pixel-to-point correspondences from step 1, the mask information is projected back onto the original 3D HPP point cloud. As a result, the target HPP component is segmented from the point cloud in a zero-shot and self-supervised manner—driven solely by a text prompt, without requiring any additional training. The method extracts one target component per prompt, and it can process multiple prompts either sequentially or simultaneously to segment several components from the same point cloud. The following sections will elaborate on the specific details of each of these steps.

3.2 | 3D to 2D

ZPSH begins by loading the input HPP point cloud model—containing each point's XYZ spatial coordinates and RGB color information—into an Open3D point cloud object. Then, the system systematically projects the 3D point cloud from 20 fixed viewpoints, which are selected based on the corners and edge midpoints of a virtual bounding cube surrounding the target point cloud, all directed toward the center of the cloud, as shown in Figure 2. This configuration is a hybrid design that fuses the principles of dodecahedron-based and cube-based uniform spherical sampling (Kanezaki et al., 2018; Kang et al., 2022), both of which are widely adopted in multi-view 3D perception for achieving near-uniform coverage with low redundancy and computing efficiency. It is important to note that the proposed framework assumes that each 3D point contains both spatial (XYZ) and color (RGB) attributes. The RGB information is required to generate semantically meaningful image renderings that can be aligned with text prompts in the CLIP embedding space.

To ensure consistent view coverage, a virtual bounding cube is defined based on the spatial extent of the input point cloud. Let X_{\max} , X_{\min} , Y_{\max} , Y_{\min} , Z_{\max} , Z_{\min} denote the minimum and maximum coordinates of all points along the three axes. The cube's edge length is set to $L = 1.2 \times \max(X_{\max} - X_{\min}, Y_{\max} - Y_{\min}, Z_{\max} - Z_{\min})$ and 20 virtual cameras are placed uniformly on its surface, each directed toward the centroid of the model. This adaptive scaling ensures that the entire structure remains within view while preserving relative geometric

FIGURE 1 Framework of the zero-shot point cloud segmentation for HPP (ZPSH).

FIGURE 2 3D to 2D mapping views (20 fixed viewpoints).

proportions across different datasets. To perform the 3D-to-2D mapping, each 3D point is first converted into homogeneous coordinates and then transformed using a view transformation matrix via matrix multiplication.

In the proposed framework, the view transformation matrix is implemented as a 4×4 affine transformation matrix that defines a virtual camera pose for each viewpoint. Specifically, each 3D point $\tilde{x} = (X, Y, Z, 1)^T$ is transformed into the camera coordinate system using: $\tilde{x}' = M_{\text{view}} \tilde{x}$ where $M_{\text{view}} = [R | t]$ combines a rotation matrix R and a translation vector t specifying the viewing direction and position of the virtual camera. Twenty predefined view matrices (8 corner and 12 edge poses) are uniformly distributed around the hydropower structure to ensure full spatial coverage. After the transformation, the projected coordinates (x', y', z') are normalized to the image plane through min-max scaling rather than using a calibrated camera-intrinsic matrix, as the goal is to maintain a geometry-only, training-free setting. Depth z' is used in a z -buffer scheme to preserve the closest point for each pixel, effectively handling occlusions. The nearest point refers to the 3D point with the smallest depth value along the viewing ray, following the standard z -buffer rule, which preserves surface visibility and prevents front-back ambiguity during projection.

FIGURE 3 RGB images from different camera views.

The resulting 2D coordinates are normalized to fit within the target image dimensions, producing corresponding RGB images (Figure 3). Additionally, for every 3D point visible in each view, its corresponding pixel coordinate (u, v) is recorded and mapped back to its original 3D coordinates. This produces a detailed 2D–3D correspondence table, which is saved as a .txt file. These generated images and mapping files form the foundational data required for the subsequent image-based segmentation and reverse projection back to the point cloud.

3.3 | Prompt-guided segmentation

Next, ZPSH leverages the cross-modal capabilities of the CLIP model to map the user-provided text prompt into the same semantic space as the image features, thereby achieving alignment between language and visual data. Specifically, the system first encodes the input text into a textual feature vector. Simultaneously, each of the 20 projected viewpoint images undergoes a sliding window process to extract multiple local image patches, each of which is encoded into an image feature vector. By computing the similarity between each image patch and the text vector, the system generates a heatmap (Figure 4) that reflects the degree of semantic alignment between different regions of the image and the input prompt. From this heatmap, the system selects the pixels with the highest similarity scores as foreground guidance points, and those with the lowest similarity as background guidance points, representing positive and negative samples for the segmentation task. Specifically, after computing the CLIP similar-

FIGURE 4 The CLIP heatmap samples in the first six views.

ity heatmap for each view, all pixels are ranked according to their similarity values with the input text prompt. The top- K and bottom- K pixels (default $K = 5$ for each category per view) are then chosen as positive and negative guidance points, respectively. These guidance points are then fed into the SAM2 segmentation model, which uses the points as prompts to perform multimodal semantic segmentation, outputting multiple candidate segmentation masks. As a result, all 20 viewpoint images are enriched with high-quality 2D semantic masks that are semantically consistent with the text prompt, laying the groundwork for the subsequent 3D semantic projection back onto the point cloud.

A key contribution of this work lies in the introduction of a novel cross-view self-learning module (CSLM) that enables consistent and robust mask selection across multiple 2D projections of a 3D point cloud, as shown in Algorithm 1. Specifically, the CSLM leverages CLIP to model both the semantic description and the visual structure of HPP components in a shared embedding space. For each candidate mask, the module uses CLIP to extract its semantic-geometric feature by encoding the masked image region. This representation is then compared—via cosine similarity—with the CLIP embedding of the input text prompt, measuring how well the masked region aligns with the implied geometry and semantics described in language. The use of cosine similarity ensures scale-invariant comparison within CLIP's normalized embedding space and is consistently applied throughout both the heatmap generation and the CSLM stages. In parallel, a cross-view consistency mechanism evaluates whether each 3D point, once marked as foreground in one view, is consistently identified as such across other views through a 2D–3D–2D reprojection process based on the stored correspondences, ensuring geometric alignment between masks before Intersection over Union (IoU) computation. To dynamically balance these

ALGORITHM 1 Cross-view self-learning module (CSLM).

$I = \{I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots\}$, Set of RGB images from n projected views.
 I_n :
 I_i : 2D RGB projection of the i th view.
 $M = \{M_1, M_2, M_3, \dots, M_n\}$: Semantic masks.
 M_i : Semantic mask of the i th view.
 P : Prompt keywords.
 b : Best MASK index.
 $S = \{S_1, S_2, S_3, \dots, S_n\}$: MASK quality score.
 S_i : Mask quality score of the i th view.
Connected components (): Extracts connected regions from the binary or semantic mask to assess spatial coherence.
GradCAM (CLIP, I_i , P): Generates a semantic attention heatmap for image I_i using the CLIP model guided by prompt P via Grad-CAM.
IoU (): Computes the Intersection over Union (Jaccard index) between two binary masks, used to measure spatial overlap.
Normalize (): Scales a raw metric to the range $[0, 1]$ to ensure consistency and comparability across different views.
 w_1, w_2, w_3 : Learnable or manually defined scalar weights for combining the three score components: connectivity, semantic alignment, and cross-view consistency.
label (M_i) = label (M_j): Ensures that cross-view consistency is computed only among masks generated under the same semantic prompt.
Input:
 $I = \{I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_n\}$
 $M = \{M_1, M_2, M_3, \dots, M_n\}$
 P
Output:
 B
 $S = \{S_1, S_2, S_3, \dots, S_n\}$
for $i = 1$ to n do
 // Step 1: Evaluate mask connectivity
 $C_i \leftarrow \text{ConnectedComponents}(M_i)$
 $r_i \leftarrow \text{maxArea}(C_i) / \text{totalMaskArea}(M_i)$
 $\text{connectivity_score} \leftarrow \text{Normalize}(r_i)$
 // Step 2: CLIP heatmap alignment
 $H_i \leftarrow \text{GradCAM}(\text{CLIP}, I_i, P)$
 $a_i \leftarrow \text{IoU}(M_i, H_i)$
 $\text{alignment_score} \leftarrow \text{Normalize}(a_i)$
 // Step 3: Cross-view consistency
 $K_i \leftarrow 0$
 for $j = 1$ to n do
 if $j \neq i$ and $\text{label}(M_i) = \text{label}(M_j)$ then

$K_i \leftarrow K_i + \text{IoU}(M_i, M_j)$
 end if
 end for
 $\text{consistency_score} \leftarrow K_i / (n - 1)$
 // Step 4: Compute final score
 $s_i \leftarrow w_1 * \text{connectivity_score} + w_2 * \text{alignment_score} + w_3 * \text{consistency_score}$
 end for
 // Step 5: Select the best view
 $b \leftarrow \text{argmax}\{S_1, S_2, S_3, \dots, S_n\}$
 return $b, \{S_1, S_2, S_3, \dots, S_n\}$

three evaluation criteria—connectivity, semantic alignment, and cross-view consistency—the CSLM employs a self-adaptive weighting mechanism. Three non-negative weights (w_1, w_2, w_3) are iteratively adjusted under the simple constraint of $w_i \geq 0$ and $\sum w_i = 1$. During mask evaluation, CSLM dynamically updates the relative weights to maximize the aggregated mask quality score S_i , as shown in Equation (1). This adaptive mechanism iteratively balances the three components until convergence to the highest overall score, from which the best-performing masks are selected for 2D–3D reverse projection.

$$S_i = w_1 \cdot \text{connectivity}_i + w_2 \cdot \text{alignment}_i + w_3 \cdot \text{consistency}_i, \quad \text{s.t. } w_i \geq 0, \sum w_i = 1 \quad (1)$$

By combining these three scores in a self-supervised fashion, the CSLM module automatically selects the most semantically aligned and structurally consistent mask for each view. This design tightly couples vision–language alignment with 3D structural consistency, making it particularly effective for prompt-based zero-shot 3D segmentation in structured industrial scenes like HPPs.

3.4 | Reverse mapping

After obtaining semantic mask images from multiple viewpoints, the third step of ZPSH is to project these 2D segmentation results back onto the 3D point cloud, thereby achieving semantic transfer from 2D to 3D. Specifically, each mask image is paired with its corresponding 2D–3D mapping file, and each 3D point accumulates foreground votes from all views in which it is visible. Instead of requiring a point to be selected in every view, ZPSH adopts a max-vote aggregation strategy, where a 3D point is recognized as a final target component if it receives the highest number of consistent foreground votes across views. This

(Continues)

FIGURE 5 Input HPP point cloud and segmented HPP component: (a) the original dam point cloud input; (b) segmented output with “spillway” as prompt (highlighted in green area).

mechanism naturally suppresses single-view noise and enforces cross-view geometric consistency without the need for a fixed threshold. To clearly display the segmentation results, all 3D points identified as belonging to the target component are simply highlighted using a uniform color (e.g., green). Background points keep their original RGB values, preserving the visual appearance of the structure. The final output is a semantic point cloud file in XYZRGB format. This completes a high-quality semantic segmentation of the 3D structure under zero-shot conditions, guided solely by a textual prompt, as illustrated in Figure 5.

3.5 | Evaluation metric

The core objective of this study is to achieve zero-shot point cloud segmentation of specific components within HPP structures. The segmentation task involves identifying all 3D points belonging to a target component from the entire background point cloud.

To quantitatively evaluate segmentation performance under this single-component setting, two ratio-based indicators are introduced: positive ratio (PR) and negative ratio (NR). Unlike the conventional IoU, which measures the overlap between predicted and ground-truth regions, PR and NR focus on the correct inclusion and false inclusion of target points relative to the true component size.

They are defined as Equations (2) and (3), where P_c denotes the predicted positive point set (points identified as belonging to the target component c), N_c denotes false-positive point set (points incorrectly included in c), and G_c denotes the ground-truth point set of component c .

Accordingly, PR measures the proportion of correctly segmented points relative to the ground-truth component, representing segmentation completeness, while NR quantifies the proportion of falsely included points relative to the same reference, representing over-segmentation severity.

$$PR_c = \frac{|P_c \cap G_c|}{|G_c|}, \quad (2)$$

FIGURE 6 Platanovrisi Hydro Power Plant in Greece: (a) front view of the dam; (b) top view of the dam point cloud.

$$NR_c = \frac{|N_c|}{|G_c|} = \frac{|P_c - G_c|}{|G_c|}. \quad (3)$$

4 | IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 | Data collection and processing

All the point cloud data used in this study were collected from the Platanovrisi Hydro Power Plant in Greece (Figure 6). The 3D point cloud data were obtained through a hybrid acquisition approach combining terrestrial laser scanning (TLS) and unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) photogrammetry. Multiple TLS stations were deployed around the dam and powerhouse area to capture detailed geometric information, while UAV-based oblique photography was used to supplement upper structures and inaccessible regions. The datasets were aligned and merged through ICP-based registration to produce a unified high-resolution point cloud with centimeter-level accuracy, suitable for large-scale hydropower infrastructure analysis.

The Platanovrisi Hydro Power Plant is a significant renewable energy infrastructure located on the Nestos River in the region of East Macedonia and Thrace, Greece. Commissioned in 1998, the plant was developed in a single phase and is currently operational. It is owned by Public Power Corporation, the main electric utility company in Greece. With a total installed capacity of 116 MW, Platanovrisi comprises two turbines, each rated at 58 MW, and supports a hydro reservoir with a storage capacity of 57 million cubic meters. The facility plays a vital role in regional power generation, delivering approximately 240 GWh of electricity annually, contributing to Greece’s renewable energy mix, and supporting its transition toward sustainable power systems. Platanovrisi exemplifies the integration of hydropower in national energy strategies, balancing environmental considerations with large-scale power production. As a long-standing asset in the Greek energy infrastructure, it reflects both the technological and environmental challenges faced by hydroelectric projects in riverine ecosystems.

4.2 | Baseline model selection and experiment setup

To validate the effectiveness and applicability of the proposed ZPSH method, this study compares it against two existing models capable of performing zero-shot 3D segmentation on HPP data. The selection criteria for the baseline models are as follows: (1) The model does not require training on multiple point cloud samples. (2) It can perform direct segmentation on HPP point cloud files without relying on additional data inputs (e.g., RGB-D information or multi-frame point clouds). (3) It is capable of handling large-scale outdoor scene point clouds and provides publicly available implementation code. Based on these criteria, this study selects clustering (Lu et al., 2016) and Point-SAM (Zhou et al., 2024) as baseline models to demonstrate the superiority of the ZPSH approach.

The detailed experimental design is as follows: First, the HPP components to be segmented are identified, and corresponding text prompts are defined (e.g., “Spillway”). These text prompts, along with the associated point cloud files, are input into the proposed ZPSH model to perform segmentation of the target components. At the same time, manual segmentation is conducted to generate the ground-truth annotations. The PR/NR metric is computed for each segmentation task using a Python script, and the results are recorded. Similarly, the same point cloud data are input into the previously mentioned baseline models for segmentation. The results are then compared against the manually annotated ground truth, and corresponding PR/NR values are recorded. It is important to note that the clustering method can only segment point clouds into spatially coherent regions and lacks direct semantic matching. Therefore, in the experiments, the largest cluster within the target region is selected as the segmentation result—representing the best-case scenario for this baseline method. This post-hoc selection is applied only for evaluation to approximate the method’s theoretical upper-bound performance. By positioning the baseline under its most favorable condition, the comparison provides a stricter benchmark, highlighting that even when the clustering approach operates at its ideal limit, the proposed ZPSH framework still achieves superior semantic segmentation results. For the Point-SAM model, since it lacks a built-in guidance point generation mechanism, the required guidance points for each target region are manually defined. This manual dependency is considered a significant limitation of the method. To ensure a fair comparison, multiple manual trials were conducted for each target component, and the best-performing segmentation result was selected as the final output. This design allows Point-SAM to operate close to its theoretical upper performance bound, minimizing the uncertainty

FIGURE 7 Segmentation results of the proposed ZPSH and baseline models (highlighted green points).

introduced by manual annotation and establishing a conservative reference against the proposed ZPSH framework. Empirically, the most effective guiding points are typically placed near the geometric center and visually distinctive regions of the target component, which yields the most coherent and stable segmentation results across different HPP scenarios. In total, the study evaluates six segmentation tasks specific to HPP scenarios, including Spillway, Downstream Face, Crest, Access Road, Outlet Works, and Environment, which refer to the natural terrain and peripheral surroundings on both sides of the dam. The six scenarios were defined based on the functional zones of the hydropower plant, covering over 90% of its visible structure. They represent distinct geometric and operational regions—such as discharge structures (Spillway, Outlet Works), dam body surfaces (Downstream Face, Crest), access infrastructure (Access Road), and contextual surroundings (Environment)—providing comprehensive coverage of real HPP inspection conditions. All experimental results are presented in Section 4.3.

4.3 | Experiment results

This section presents a comparative analysis of the point cloud segmentation performance of the proposed ZPSH method against the baseline models across six different HPP-specific scenarios. Table 2 and Figure 7 summarize the detailed segmentation results obtained from the experiments.

TABLE 2 Comparison of the proposed ZPSH and baseline models segmentation results.

Experiment models	Target point number	PR (%) (Positive segmented)	NR (%) (Negative segmented)
Total point cloud number: 4,108,087			
Scenarios 1: Spillway			
Clustering	57,181	10.24%	0.00%
Point-SAM	57,181	80.35%	32.41%
ZPSH (our)	57,181	85.32%	17.35%
Scenarios 2: Downstream face			
Clustering	67,414	21.46%	0%
Point-SAM	67,414	84.34%	47.63%
ZPSH (our)	67,414	83.88%	61.01%
Scenarios 3: Crest			
Clustering	55,090	4.56%	0%
Point-SAM	55,090	18.56%	24.03%
ZPSH (our)	55,090	22.45%	4.38%
Scenarios 4: Access road			
Clustering	17,450	14.00%	0%
Point-SAM	17,450	65.36%	241.07%
ZPSH (our)	17,450	85.15%	15.19%
Scenarios 5: Outlet works			
Clustering	14,166	8.43%	0%
Point-SAM	14,166	31.70%	63.07%
ZPSH (our)	14,166	66.37%	6.69%
Scenarios 6: Environment			
Clustering	199,780	14.44%	0%
Point-SAM	199,780	89.01%	10.81%
ZPSH (our)	199,780	92.21%	16.08%

Bold represents the best performances.

Overall, the three models exhibit significant performance differences in segmentation tasks: The clustering method, as a traditional unsupervised approach, consistently demonstrates low PR across all scenarios (with a maximum of only 21.46%) and a zero NR throughout. This indicates that the method struggles to effectively distinguish between target and non-target regions, showing very limited segmentation capability. The Point-SAM model, built on pre-trained segmentation mechanisms, generally outperforms clustering, with relatively high PR in some scenarios. For instance, it achieves 89.01% in the Environment scenario and 84.34% in the Downstream Face scenario. However, it exhibits large fluctuations in NR, with values reaching as high as 241.07% in the Access Road scenario. This suggests issues with over-segmentation or misclassification of background regions, reflecting limited robustness. In contrast, the proposed ZPSH method delivers the best overall performance. It consistently achieves the highest PR across most scenarios, exceeding 80% accu-

racy in the majority of cases and maintaining robust performance in challenging scenes such as Spillway and Access Road. Moreover, ZPSH demonstrates strong stability in NR, remaining within a reasonable range—6.69% in Outlet Works and 15.19% in Access Road—substantially better than the extreme variations observed in Point-SAM.

These results indicate that ZPSH is more precise in distinguishing between target and non-target regions and possesses superior generalization and robustness. In summary, ZPSH not only enhances segmentation accuracy but also exhibits greater stability in complex HPP scenarios, significantly outperforming existing baseline methods in comprehensive performance.

5 | DISCUSSION

5.1 | Positive and negative cases

To further validate the effectiveness of the proposed method, this section conducts a case-based analysis by examining both positive cases (scenarios with high segmentation performance) and negative cases (scenarios with lower performance). The goal is to explore the performance variation of the ZPSH model across different HPP scenarios and to investigate the underlying factors contributing to these differences.

5.1.1 | Positive cases

Among the various test scenarios in this study, the Access Road and Outlet Works target regions demonstrate the significant advantages of the ZPSH model in point cloud segmentation tasks, highlighting its strong adaptability to different structural types.

The Access Road, which connects dam facilities to external areas, typically exhibits features such as narrow width, linear shape, and curved paths. It has a relatively small volume and is easily confused with the surrounding natural terrain, making it a challenging target for segmentation. In contrast, the Outlet Works is a complex and densely structured outflow system of the dam, comprising spillways, bottom outlets, guide channels, and other functional zones. It features irregular boundaries and heterogeneous internal structures, demanding high levels of detail preservation and spatial reasoning from the segmentation model. Despite the stark differences in their geometric characteristics and semantic complexity, ZPSH achieved excellent segmentation results in both scenarios.

In the Access Road scenario, ZPSH attained a PR of 85.15% and an NR of only 15.19%, significantly outperforming Point-SAM's NR of 241.07%, effectively avoid-

FIGURE 8 CLIP heatmaps (top) and corresponding SAM-based segmentation (bottom) for positive (Access Road, Outlet Works) and negative (Crest, Downstream Face) cases.

ing the inclusion of background noise. In the Outlet Works scenario, ZPSH achieved 66.37% PR and 6.69% NR, again surpassing Point-SAM's results of 31.70% and 63.07%, respectively, demonstrating both higher segmentation precision and stability. The visual comparison of CLIP heatmaps and segmentation results for the Access Road and Outlet Works (Figure 8) further supports this observation. In both cases, SAM2 produces compact and well-confined masks that accurately follow the geometric boundaries of the target components.

The success of ZPSH in these cases can be attributed to several key factors: (1) CSLM enhances geometric robustness: By acquiring foreground guidance points across multiple views and reprojecting the 2D segmentation results into 3D space, ZPSH significantly reduces the influence of occlusions and viewpoint bias on segmentation quality. (2) CLIP-guided semantic prompting improves contextual awareness: The foreground heatmaps generated through language–image matching effectively guide the SAM model to focus on critical regions of the target object, preventing misidentification of background areas that are semantically similar but irrelevant. (3) Strong adaptability to structural variability: ZPSH demonstrates balanced generalization capabilities, performing well on both the linear boundaries of Access Roads and the complex boundaries of Outlet Works—highlighting its ability to handle diverse object types.

In summary, these two positive case studies provide strong evidence that the ZPSH method maintains high accuracy and low error even when faced with drastically different point cloud structures. This reflects the model's robustness, semantic understanding, and overall stability in complex HPP environments.

5.1.2 | Negative cases

Despite the strong overall performance of the ZPSH model across most scenarios, it still faces challenges in scenes with complex structures or ambiguous boundaries. To better illustrate the limitations of the method, this subsection highlights representative failure cases and categorizes the main causes of segmentation errors, including boundary ambiguity, low-texture regions, and cross-view inconsistencies.

The Crest refers to the top horizontal section of the dam, often used as a walkway or maintenance platform. Although geometrically simple, this area exhibits ambiguous boundaries and frequently overlaps with background platforms or railings. This results in strong visual and geometric continuity between target and non-target regions. In this scene, ZPSH achieved only 22.45% PR and 4.38% NR. While marginally outperforming Point-SAM, the segmentation accuracy remains low. The predicted regions suffer from incomplete contours and significant omissions. The Downstream Face refers to the sloped or vertical face of the dam on the downstream side, typically large in scale, made of uniform materials, and lacking clear structural boundaries. It is often affected by shadows, angle occlusion, and viewpoint distortion. In this scenario, ZPSH achieved a relatively high PR of 83.88%, but a high NR of 61.01%, indicating that many background points were mistakenly included, suggesting a case of over-segmentation. This pattern is also reflected in the heatmap–segmentation visualization (Figure 8), where the Crest and Downstream Face exhibit diffuse or misleading CLIP activations, which correlate with incomplete contours or background leakage in the final segmentation.

These issues may stem from several factors: (1) Semantic uncertainty caused by ambiguous boundaries: In the Crest scenario, the absence of clear geometric discontinuities between the target and background makes it difficult for CLIP to produce focused foreground guidance points. This leads to imprecise segmentation in downstream processing. (2) Limited feature expression in 2D projections: In large, textureless regions like the Downstream Face, the 2D projections lack sufficient structural features. As a result, both CLIP and SAM struggle to extract meaningful semantics across multiple views. (3) Misguided foreground prompting due to background similarity: Especially in high-angle or distant viewpoints, background elements may share similar color or material properties with the target, leading CLIP to misidentify background as foreground, thus inflating NR.

These negative cases highlight that, while ZPSH performs well in many settings, there is still room

TABLE 3 Reseeding stability of self-learning weights (w_1, w_2, w_3) in CSLM (five random seeds, fixed data and hyperparameters).

Run (Seed)	w_1 (Connectivity)	w_2 (Alignment)	w_3 (Consistency)	Average PR (%)	Average NR (%)
0	0.30	0.47	0.23	81.4	20.1
1	0.28	0.45	0.27	83.2	19.3
2	0.33	0.44	0.23	83.9	18.8
3	0.32	0.46	0.22	80.1	20.0
4	0.30	0.43	0.27	80.5	19.2
<i>Mean ± Std</i>	0.306 ± 0.0195	0.450 ± 0.0158	0.244 ± 0.0241	81.820 ± 1.6664	19.480 ± 0.5541

Mean represents the arithmetic mean, and *Std* represents the standard deviation. All reported *PR* and *NR* values are averaged across the six testing scenarios.

for improvement in terms of boundary refinement, background suppression, and guidance point filtering—particularly in scenarios where the target structure is visually indistinct or structurally diffuse.

5.2 | Weight sensitivity and stability analysis

To further assess the robustness of the self-adaptive weighting mechanism in the CSLM, a reseeding stability experiment using five different random initializations under identical data and hyperparameter settings was performed. For each run, the three weights (w_1, w_2, w_3)—representing connectivity, semantic alignment, and cross-view consistency—were adaptively optimized following the self-supervised procedure described in Section 3.3. As summarized in Table 3, the learned weights remained stable across different random seeds.

The results (Table 3) show that the learned weights remained consistent across runs ($w_1 = 0.306 \pm 0.0195$, $w_2 = 0.450 \pm 0.0158$, $w_3 = 0.244 \pm 0.0241$), and the corresponding segmentation performance varied only slightly (PR = $81.82\% \pm 1.6664\%$, NR = $19.48\% \pm 0.5541\%$), demonstrating that CSLM's optimization process converges consistently and is largely insensitive to initialization randomness. These results indicate that the self-adaptive weighting mechanism achieves a reliable equilibrium among geometric, semantic, and cross-view cues, thereby contributing to the overall robustness of the proposed ZPSH framework.

5.3 | Computational cost and scalability analysis

To evaluate the computational efficiency and scalability of the proposed ZPSH framework, the total processing time and peak memory usage across six representative scenarios were measured. All experiments were conducted on a workstation running Windows 11 Pro, equipped with an Intel Core Ultra 9 185H CPU (2.3 GHz), 32 GB RAM, and

an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4070 Laptop GPU (8 GB VRAM). The pipeline consists of three major stages: (1) 3D-to-2D projection, (2) prompt-guided segmentation using CLIP and SAM 2, and (3) reverse mapping for 2D–3D consistency reconstruction.

As summarized in Table 4, the proposed method demonstrates a practical computational profile even for large-scale point clouds containing over 4.1 million points. The end-to-end runtime for the entire pipeline is approximately 115 minutes, while the average per-view inference time is around 50 seconds. Peak memory usage remained low throughout the pipeline, with CPU consumption stable at approximately 1.9 GB and GPU usage peaking at 2.4 GB during the reverse mapping stage, where dense 2D–3D projection computations are performed. This demonstrates that the system can efficiently handle large-scale datasets without excessive resource demand.

These results verify that the proposed framework is computationally feasible for engineering-scale HPP application component inspection, where millions of points and multiple viewpoints are common. The consistent runtime and memory footprint across all scenarios further support the scalability and deployment potential of ZPSH in real-world environments.

5.4 | Prompt sensitivity analysis

To evaluate the robustness of ZPSH under different linguistic expressions, a prompt sensitivity analysis was conducted. For each semantic class, three semantically equivalent text prompts were selected to represent different but related wordings (e.g., “Spillway,” “Chute,” and “Sluiceway”). The model was evaluated using each prompt independently, and the resulting segmentation metrics were summarized in Table 5.

As shown in Table 5, ZPSH exhibits varying sensitivity to prompt wording across semantic classes. In most cases, the model maintains reasonable robustness to linguistic variations, yet certain categories remain highly prompt-dependent. For instance, in the Spillway scenario, semantically similar prompts—“Spillway,” “Chute,”

TABLE 4 Computational cost of the proposed ZPSH pipeline across six scenarios (20 views for each scene).

Scene	Points	Total time (s)	CPU peak (GB)	GPU peak (GB)	Time per view (s)
3D to 2D					
All (same)	4,108,087	215.310	0.000	1.021	10.766
Prompt-guided segmentation					
Spillway	57,181	1068.077	1.947	1.903	53.404
Downstream face	67,414	1127.141	1.947	1.903	56.357
Crest	55,090	921.782	1.947	1.903	46.089
Access road	17,450	1036.204	1.947	1.903	51.810
Outlet works	14,166	879.194	1.947	1.903	43.960
Environment	199,780	943.617	1.947	1.903	47.181
Revers mapping					
All (same)	4,108,087	740.941	0.000	2.426	37.047

All experiments were conducted on a workstation running Windows 11 Pro, equipped with an Intel Core Ultra 9 185H CPU (2.3 GHz), 32 GB RAM, and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4070 Laptop GPU (8 GB VRAM).

TABLE 5 Prompt sensitivity analysis across all semantic classes.

Prompt	PR (%)	Mean PR \pm Std (%)	NR (%)	Mean NR \pm Std (%)
Scenarios 1: Spillway				
Spillway	85.32%	61.29 \pm 44.42%	17.35%	35.30 \pm 17.71%
Chute	10.03%	61.29 \pm 44.42%	52.76%	35.30 \pm 17.71%
Sluiceway	88.53%	61.29 \pm 44.42%	35.78%	35.30 \pm 17.71%
Scenarios 2: Downstream face				
Downstream face	83.88%	72.87 \pm 9.58%	61.01%	48.10 \pm 14.09%
Downstream slope	68.25%	72.87 \pm 9.58%	33.07%	48.10 \pm 14.09%
Downstream facade	66.48%	72.87 \pm 9.58%	50.23%	48.10 \pm 14.09%
Scenarios 3: Crest				
Crest	22.45%	18.44 \pm 4.51%	4.38%	9.13 \pm 4.41%
Dam ridge	13.55%	18.44 \pm 4.51%	9.92%	9.13 \pm 4.41%
Dam crest	19.32%	18.44 \pm 4.51%	13.10%	9.13 \pm 4.41%
Scenarios 4: Access road				
Access road	85.15%	76.26 \pm 14.09%	15.19%	14.20 \pm 5.25%
Accessway	60.02%	76.26 \pm 14.09%	8.53%	14.20 \pm 5.25%
Entry road	83.62%	76.26 \pm 14.09%	18.88%	14.20 \pm 5.25%
Scenarios 5: Outlet works				
Outlet works	66.37%	74.41 \pm 7.01%	6.69%	16.85 \pm 9.42%
Outlet gates	79.23%	74.41 \pm 7.01%	18.55%	16.85 \pm 9.42%
Release gates	72.62%	74.41 \pm 7.01%	25.30%	16.85 \pm 9.42%
Scenarios 6: Environment				
Environment	83.51%	80.45 \pm 13.56%	27.33%	24.05 \pm 6.94%
Flanking hills	65.62%	80.45 \pm 13.56%	28.75%	24.05 \pm 6.94%
Adjacent mountains	92.21%	80.45 \pm 13.56%	16.08%	24.05 \pm 6.94%

Each class is evaluated using three semantically equivalent text prompts. Results are reported as mean PR/NR with standard deviation across prompt variants.

and “Sluiceway”—yield PR values of 85.32%, 10.03%, and 88.53%, respectively ($\pm 44.42\%$), indicating strong sensitivity to wording. Conversely, Outlet works show stable performance (66.37% to 79.23%, $\pm 7.01\%$) since its descrip-

tors share clearer and more distinctive semantics. This variation arises mainly because CLIP’s textual embeddings capture general visual semantics, but domain-specific terms like “Chute” are less aligned with hydropower con-

texts, leading to weak activation in cross-modal similarity maps.

Overall, these results reveal that ZPSH remains robust to moderate linguistic differences but is affected when prompt tokens deviate from CLIP's learned visual-language space or overlap semantically with background objects. Enhancing text-image embedding alignment or incorporating adaptive prompt refinement could further mitigate such sensitivity.

5.5 | Limitations

Although the ZPSH model demonstrates excellent performance in segmenting point clouds with complex structures, this study still faces several notable limitations, primarily reflected in the following aspects: (1) Unstable performance in identifying ambiguous boundaries: In scenarios such as Crest, where there is strong spatial continuity between target and background, the model struggles to accurately delineate boundaries. This often leads to sparse or misaligned guidance points, ultimately reducing segmentation accuracy. These results suggest that ZPSH still lacks sufficient capability to capture target contours in geometrically indistinct regions. (2) Heavy reliance on viewpoint quality and prompt selection: The segmentation performance of ZPSH depends heavily on the quality of heatmaps and foreground guidance points generated by CLIP. Since the model requires RGB-enriched point clouds for rendering multi-view projections, its performance may degrade on datasets that contain only grayscale or intensity information, where semantic cues are less distinguishable. In addition, when the 2D projection viewpoint is too distant, or when the target is subject to occlusion or poor lighting conditions, the semantic guidance may be distorted, leading to errors in the SAM segmentation process and the subsequent 3D fusion. (3) Lack of semantic consistency constraints across views: Currently, prompt generation and segmentation are performed independently for each viewpoint. Although cross-view integration is implemented via the CSLM module, there is no explicit mechanism enforcing global semantic consistency. This can result in inconsistent mask quality for the same target across different views, which may affect the stability of the final 3D segmentation. Incorporating transformer-based or multi-scale attention mechanisms could further strengthen global feature aggregation and improve overall consistency in future extensions. (4) Domain-specific semantic limitation. Since CLIP was pretrained mainly on natural image-text pairs, its capacity to fully capture the semantics of hydropower-related components is limited. Certain specialized terms, such as spillway, abutment, or crest, may not have strong

textual-visual associations in the pretrained embedding space, occasionally leading to weaker or ambiguous similarity responses. However, in practice, the distinctive geometry and spatial configuration of these structures still allow the model to produce meaningful segmentation results, especially when reinforced by the multi-view consistency enforced by CSLM. Future work will focus on enhancing domain adaptability through prompt engineering, domain-specific vocabulary expansion, and fine-tuning of multimodal encoders using engineering imagery and documentation. (5) Generalization and data acquisition challenges. Acquiring large-scale, high-quality point clouds in hydropower environments is inherently challenging due to the vast spatial extent, complex topography, and multi-scale structural composition of such facilities. In addition, hydropower plants are critical infrastructure, where data collection is often subject to strict access control, safety regulations, and confidentiality restrictions. These practical constraints make multi-site data acquisition extremely difficult. Nevertheless, the collected dataset already covers diverse structural components and material variations representative of typical hydropower facilities. Moreover, the proposed ZPSH framework is prompt-driven and does not rely on site-specific training data, allowing it to be readily adapted to other industrial scenarios. Future work will focus on expanding the dataset to multiple hydropower stations with different environmental and structural conditions to further enhance model generalization.

5.6 | Future work

Building on the current findings and acknowledging the existing limitations, future research can be extended in the following directions:

(1) *Incorporating boundary-aware mechanisms*: This issue arises mainly from incomplete semantic contrast between adjacent regions in 2D projections and weak gradient responses in CLIP-based similarity maps. When neighboring components share similar geometric or color characteristics (e.g., the crest and downstream face), their projected boundaries tend to lack clear text-image separation, resulting in uncertainty within the heatmap and subsequent segmentation. In such situations, the current CSLM relies primarily on the most confident view-level masks, which may propagate local inconsistencies if all views exhibit similar ambiguity. This limitation reflects a fundamental challenge of prompt-based zero-shot segmentation methods—the absence of explicit boundary supervision. To overcome this, future research will explore cross-view boundary refinement and gradient-aware attention alignment to enhance local edge discrimination.

Another promising direction is to incorporate a geometry-aware fusion mechanism that integrates normal or curvature cues during reverse mapping, improving spatial coherence and boundary precision in 3D reconstruction.

(2) *Optimizing multi-view semantic fusion strategies:* The current CSLM assumes uniformly distributed viewpoints and adopts an equal-weight averaging scheme for cross-view consistency. This simplification may reduce sensitivity to geometric distance and visibility variation in complex or asymmetric structures. Future extensions could incorporate distance- or overlap-weighted consistency evaluation, in which pairwise IoU calculations are adaptively scaled by spatial proximity and shared projection ratio between viewpoints. Such an enhancement would improve geometric awareness and strengthen the robustness of multi-view semantic alignment, particularly for large-scale hydropower structures with non-uniform spatial coverage.

(3) *Designing adaptive guidance point filtering:* After generating heatmaps, an additional step could be introduced to evaluate the confidence of guidance points and filter out low-quality candidates, ensuring that the prompts fed into the SAM model are both representative and informative.

(4) *Extending to multi-class and condition-aware segmentation:* The present study primarily targets hydropower-specific components (e.g., spillway, crest, and gate), whose segmentation cannot be reliably achieved using conventional geometric methods such as normal-based plane fitting or region growing. Future research will aim to generalize the proposed framework beyond component-level segmentation by incorporating state-aware and descriptive language prompts (e.g., rusted, cracked, and corroded), thereby enabling condition-level understanding. This extension will require the integration of richer visual cues—such as color, texture, or multispectral features—alongside geometric information, paving the way toward multimodal, degradation-aware 3D inspection of large-scale industrial assets. Although the current implementation adopts a prompt-wise single-class segmentation strategy, the modular architecture of ZPSH allows future extension toward multi-class or multi-prompt segmentation for real-world hydropower scenarios.

(5) *Developing hybrid learning strategies.* Future research could focus on semi-supervised or hybrid learning frameworks to enhance boundary precision while retaining zero-shot adaptability for engineering scenarios. Another promising direction lies in scalable point cloud acquisition and annotation strategies for hydropower plants, since the diverse geometries of HPP components require extensive, high-quality labeled datasets to fully leverage supervised learning approaches.

6 | CONCLUSION

This study presents ZPSH, a novel zero-shot 3D point cloud segmentation framework specifically designed for HPP scenarios. Unlike existing supervised or unsupervised methods that rely on large, annotated datasets or auxiliary multimodal inputs, ZPSH performs accurate, high-resolution segmentation of industrial components solely based on point cloud data and a user-defined text prompt. By integrating multi-view projection, CLIP-based semantic prompting, SAM2-guided mask generation, and a CSLM, ZPSH effectively bridges the gap between natural language understanding and geometric perception in complex industrial environments.

Experiments on real-world HPP point clouds demonstrate that ZPSH significantly outperforms traditional clustering and recent zero-shot baselines in both PR and NR, delivering robust and semantically consistent segmentation across diverse component types—including narrow linear structures (e.g., access roads) and dense heterogeneous regions (e.g., outlet works). Failure case analyses, such as in crest and downstream face segmentation, further reveal the model's strengths and its current limitations regarding boundary ambiguity, prompt reliability, and inter-view consistency.

In summary, this work contributes to the field of HPP infrastructure DT by introducing a practical, scalable, and annotation-free solution for industrial 3D segmentation. ZPSH enables fully automated, prompt-driven creation of high-fidelity DTs, which are critical for intelligent planning, monitoring, and operation of hydropower and other civil infrastructure projects. By reducing human effort, eliminating the need for costly annotations, and improving adaptability to complex industrial environments, ZPSH lays the groundwork for integrating advanced AI techniques into automated construction workflows and decision support systems. Although demonstrated using hydropower plant data, the proposed framework is general and transferable to other large-scale industrial or civil infrastructure scenarios that share similar characteristics of geometric complexity and sparse labeling. Future work will focus on enhancing boundary sensitivity, improving prompt robustness, and extending the model's capabilities to multi-class segmentation and real-world streaming sensor data.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported in part by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101122357 (D-HYDROFLEX). Funded by the European Union. We also gratefully acknowl-

edge the support of PPC (Public Power Corporation S.A., Greece) for this work.

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How to cite this article: Su, Y., Chen, W., Ling, J., & Yu, D. (2025). Zero-shot point cloud segmentation for hydro power plant components. *Computer-Aided Civil and Infrastructure Engineering*, 40, 6261–6278. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mice.70150>